

Structural Integrity of Composite Manipulator Applied to the Automated Ropeway Inspection Using Flexible Multibody Dynamics Analysis

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ABSTRACT

- In this study, the structural design and structural integrity evaluation of CFRP frame applied to a ropeway structure inspection manipulator were conducted. The ropeway structure inspection manipulator is a device that remotely inspects defects and wear of ropeway wheel devices of rope facilities used as transportation, such as cable cars or ski lifts.
- In the case of the existing ropeway structure inspection manipulator, it was made of aluminum, but in order to lightweight of the manipulator and reduce deflection, the existing aluminum material was replaced with CFRP material. In order to apply CFRP materials to manipulators, the stiffness design of the CFRP frame is essential, and structural integrity evaluation due to the external environment occurring during inspection and the load generated during operating motion also be secured. For the motion reflected in the analysis, the maximum deflection of the end device equipped with the camera was confirmed in the motion state where the inspection manipulator, which occurred to have the maximum deflection, was horizontally spread out.
- To evaluate the structural integrity of the CFRP frame reflecting the actual inspection environment based on the selected stacking pattern, flexible multibody dynamics analysis (FMDB) was performed. The maximum wind loads and railway wheel structure inspection motion in the actual inspection environment were applied according to the Facility Standards for Construction and Equipment for Tramway Facilities' Regulations. structural integrity was confirmed.

INTRODUCTION

Background and significance

- A ropeway system is a transportation method that uses wire ropes to carry passengers or cargo. To ensure optimal performance, regular inspections of ropeway systems are essential.
- Traditionally, ropeway inspections were performed manually by workers. However, recent research has focused on developing remote robotic ropeway inspection systems to enhance worker's safety and maintain consistent operational efficiency.
- The manipulator attached to the inspection robot is equipped with a camera mounted on its end effector, enabling remote inspection of rope structures. As the robot moves along the facility's wire ropes, lightweight design is essential for efficient operation.
- In this study, to achieve both lightweight construction and structural integrity, carbon fiber based on composite materials with high specific stiffness and strength were applied to the manipulator components. The structural integrity was evaluated through flexible multibody dynamic analysis, considering actual operating conditions.

METHODS

Design for manipulator stacking pattern and deflection analysis

- For laminated composites, the stacking pattern and fiber orientation can be designed according to the designer's specifications. Consequently, the strength and stiffness of the structure under external loads vary depending on the lamination pattern.
- Since ropeway structures are exposed to complex loading conditions, the lamination pattern and thickness were set as design variables considering the composite manufacturing environment. Optimal lamination patterns were selected through deflection analysis of the manipulator's end tool.

Fig. 3. Components of manipulator

- The deflection amounts based on the layup patterns presented in Table 1 were compared. For the motion environment, deflection analysis was performed under the condition shown in Fig. 3, where the manipulator is fully extended horizontally, causing maximum deflection at the end effector.

Table.1 Description of stacking pattern

Pattern	Stacking Pattern [Carbon(H2550)/Epoxy Composite]	Deflection of end tool [mm]
Pattern 1	[0/90] _{10T}	8.112
Pattern 2	[0 ₃ /±30] _s	5.168
Pattern 3	[0/90/±45/+45] _s	4.875
Pattern 4	[0/90/±45/0] _s	4.061

- Based on the deflection analysis results for each layup pattern, the [0/90/±45/0]_s layup configuration was selected. Subsequently, deflection analysis was performed and compared for varying composite thicknesses.
- As a result, the optimal composite thicknesses were determined to be 4T/3T/3T, which maximize the stiffness of the manipulator while satisfying the design mass criteria.

Table.2 Results of deflection analysis for link thickness

Case	Link1 Thickness	Link2 Thickness	Link3 Thickness	Mass [kg]	Deflection of Endtool [mm]
Case1	3T	3T	3T	3.106	2.832
Case2	4T	4T	4T	4.141	1.980
Case3	4T	4T	3T	3.912	2.036
Case4	4T	4T	2T	3.682	2.189
Case5	4T	3T	3T	3.576	2.262
Case6	4T	3T	2T	3.346	2.410
Case7	4T	2T	2T	3.010	2.901

Fig. 4. Comparison of total mass and deflection

Structural Integrity evaluation of composite manipulator

- The structural integrity of the manipulator's composite link is evaluated using flexible multibody dynamics analysis.
- The applied loads include forces generated by the motion during ropeway structure inspection and the maximum wind load, as specified by facility standard regulations for the construction of track facilities.

Fig. 5. Inspection motion of the manipulator

- Joint conditions were created to fully constrain the links and motors for flexible multibody dynamics analysis and motor conditions were created using the Altair Inspire program.
- At Time 0.06 sec, the motion time when the maximum load and moment occur, the absolute max. Principal stress of 32.84 MPa was derived from the third CFRP link, and the maximum displacement of 0.249 mm was confirmed.

Fig. 6. Absolute Max. principal stress of FMDB link3

Fig. 7. Displacement of FMDB Link3

RESULTS

- In order to verify the reliability of the results derived from flexible multibody dynamics (FMDB) and structural analysis, the maximum principal stress and displacement results were compared.
- As the result of analysis, the maximum principal stress and displacement results between flexible multibody dynamics and structural analysis were confirmed to be the same, verifying the reliability.

Fig. 8. Results of flexible multibody dynamic analysis(FMDB)

Fig. 9. Results of static analysis

- The Tsai-Wu Index of each manipulator CFRP link in the composite part was confirmed to be up to 0.079, confirming structural integrity.

Fig. 10. Results of static analysis for composite manipulator

Fig. 11. Maximum Tsai-Wu Index of CFRP link

CONCLUSION

Summary

- In this study, the optimal composite stacking sequence and laminate thickness were determined to ensure the structural stiffness of the manipulator through deflection analysis. Furthermore, the structural integrity under complex loading conditions generated during the manipulator's inspection motion was evaluated. The failure analysis of the CFRP components under the maximum load and moment conditions was conducted using the Tsai-Wu failure criterion. The Tsai-Wu failure index remained below 1.0 for all CFRP links, validating the structural integrity of the manipulator design.

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